

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OPEJO****FIRST NAME: PIUS****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D PERIOD 1-5

1. Out of the many citation style guides, select one recommended by Euclid University from those listed below

- American Psychological Association (APA)
- Chicago styles (Turabian)¹**
- Harvard style
- American Chemical Society

2. Rules of thumb while writing an academic paper include one of the following

- Explore various theories or topics at the same time
- Lead or conclude with sweeping statements

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK: PERIOD 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

- You do not need to support assertions
- Do not do plagiarism²**
3. Which of the following is correct regarding academic essay writing?
- Seeks to provide an answer(s) to hypothesis aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence³**
- Fictional type of essay writing
- Academic essay is different from scholarly writing
- All academic essays must be published in peer-reviewed journals
4. Choose one correct statement below regarding the hypothesis in the dissertation writing
- References must be made for every hypothesis
- Both quantitative and qualitative research must clearly state their hypotheses
- A null hypothesis assumes that there is no difference among variables whereas a directional hypothesis assumes that any significant difference among variables and participant groups is in a specific direction based on the theory or prior research⁴**
- Data can be analyzed by any means without regard to hypothesis

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 7.

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 35.

5. Regarding measures and validity in quantitative research, one of the following is correct
- Face validity is concerned with congruence between what an instrument or test actually measures and what it is designed to measure
 - Content validity documents evidence that the content of the measure is congruent with conceptual and theoretical basis of instrument or test or study tool⁵**
 - Factorial validity documents evidence that the individuals perceive that an instrument or study tool appears to measure what it is intended to do.
 - Measures have no direct contribution to research bias
6. Comparing quantitative and qualitative research, tick the correct statement from the list provided below
- Relevancy as applied to qualitative research is similar to validity as applied to quantitative research⁶**
 - Plausibility and relevancy have the same meaning and can be used interchangeably as in qualitative research
 - Coherency is crucial for a researcher but not important to a reader
 - Credibility and competency explain the same attributes in qualitative research

⁵ Sampson, 40.

⁶ Sampson, 43.

7. A researcher writing his or her dissertation targeting European Commission territory is encouraged to use one of the following guides for spelling checks
- Advanced Learner's Dictionary prefers British and American English spelling because the English used in postgraduate writing must be advanced
 - Oxford's English Dictionary on Lexicon, prefers the British and world English spelling to North American⁷**
 - Cambridge English dictionary
 - Any available English reference text, as long as the researcher finds it useful
8. While defining your research project, you should endeavor to pay attention to one of the following
- You should start it well before searching the internet or library and continue even after the required data has been collected⁸**
 - You should start it in the last semester of your course and stop immediately after your team has collected the required data
 - You should always search as extensively as possible while exploring all possible data; focusing on specific topics risks limiting your scope significantly
 - You should limit your search to primary sources only. Other sources, such as secondary and tertiary, will overwhelm you, slowing down your progress

⁷ Tim Cooper et al., *European Commission English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (European Union, 2021), 17.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 24.

9. When a researcher is looking for creative agreement, it is crucial to do one of the following

- Any claim provided by the source should not be applied widely
- You do not need to confirm unsupported claims
- You can offer new evidence to support a source's claim⁹**
- Only your claim is the most important

10. While drafting a paper, a researcher should endeavor to pay attention to one of the following;

- A researcher should be careful not to integrate quotations into their texts
- A researcher should try as much as possible to use Footnotes and Endnotes judiciously¹⁰**
- A researcher does not have to show the relevance of the complex and detailed evidence
- A researcher should avoid being open to new ideas and surprises to minimize chances of confusion

⁹ Turabian et al., 46.

¹⁰ Turabian et al., 79.

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